

MOST IMPORTANT POINTS IN DICTIONARY COMPILING

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Annotation: In this article the most important ten tasks are mentioned in dictionary compiling. They are selecting words, their spelling, pronunciation, meanings, grammatical features and others essential points are discussed.

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Today every language learner needs a good dictionary without which it is impossible to learn a language. But dictionary compiling is one of the most difficult and important tasks. Lexicographers should pay attention to some points when compiling dictionaries, now we are going to mention them.

1. The obsolete and archaic words must be included from the earlier stages of the language and even the words attested to only once (nonce words). In a language with a large literature, many “uncollected words” are likely to remain, lurking in out-of-the-way sources. Also, the so-called latent words are a problem, when a lexicographer knows that a derivative word probably has been used, but he has no evidence for it. The first edition of the OED had three quotations for kindheartedness but none for kindheartedly, which any speaker of English would feel free to use. Some “ghost words” have arisen from the misreading of manuscripts and from misprints, and the lexicographer attempts to cast these out.

2. Dictionaries have probably played an important role in establishing the conventions of English spelling. Johnson has received much credit for this, though he differed very little from his predecessors. He used the spelling *smoak* in the early part of his dictionary, but when he came to the entry itself he changed it to *smoke*, and this has prevailed. Noah Webster introduced some simplifications that have become accepted in American English. American dictionaries usually label the distinctive British spellings, such as *centre* and *its class*, *honour* and *its class*, *connexion*, *gaol*, *kerb*, *tyre*, *waggon*, and a few others.

3. Dictionaries are more responsive to usage in the matter of pronunciation than they are in spelling. It is claimed that in the 19th century the Merriam-Webster dictionaries foisted a New England pronunciation on the United States, but by the mid-20th century many regional variations had been recorded. Webster’s Third New International went to surprising lengths in its variants; perhaps its record is in giving 132 different ways of pronouncing *a fortiori*.

4.The supplying of etymologies involves such difficult decisions for a lexicographer as whether words should be carried back into prehistory by means of reconstructed forms or the degree to which speculation should be permitted. An American Romance scholar, Yakov Malkiel, presented the notion that words follow “trajectories”—by finding certain points in the history of a word, one can link up the developments in form and meaning. The austere treatment of some words consists in saying “derivation unknown,” and yet this sometimes causes interesting possibilities to be ignored.

5.Dictionaries are obliged to contain the two basic types of words of a language—the “function words” (those that perform the grammatical functions in a language, such as the articles, pronouns, prepositions, and conjunctions) and the “referential words” (those that symbolize entities outside the language system). Each type must be treated in a suitable way. Dictionaries have been much criticized for not including a sufficiency of grammatical information. It is usual to mark the part of speech, but not the categories of mass noun and count noun. (A mass noun, such as milk or oxygen, cannot ordinarily be used in the plural, while a count noun is any noun that can be pluralized.) Such information is given in some dictionaries designed for teaching, and the technique could well be adopted more generally. The irregular inflections must be given, showing that one says goose, geese, but not moose, meese. Or in the verbs, one says walk, walked, but ride, rode. It is usual to treat the different parts of speech as separate lexical entries, as in “to walk” and “to take a walk,” requiring a parallel list of senses, but Thorndike, in his school dictionaries, experimented with grouping the parts of speech together when they had a similar sense.

6.A language like English has so many complex developments in the senses—i.e., the particular meanings—of its words that the task of the lexicographer is difficult. It is generally accepted that “meaning” is a suffusing characteristic of all language by definition, and the attempt to slice meaning into “senses” must be done arbitrarily by the person analyzing the language. This is where collected contexts form the basis of the lexicographer’s judgment. The lexicographer sorts the quotations into piles on the basis of similarities and differences and may have to discard “transitional” examples. Figurative developments, such as the mouth of a river or the foot of a hill, make complications in the relationships.

7.Part of the information that a dictionary should give concerns the restrictions and constraints on the use of words, commonly called usage labelling. There is great variation in language use in many dimensions—temporal, geographical, and cultural. The people who make a two-part division into “correct” and “incorrect” show that they do not understand how language works. The valuation does not lie in the word itself but in the appropriateness of the context. Therefore, it is preferable to be

sparing in the use of labels and to allow the tone to become apparent from the illustrative examples. An important distinction was put forward in 1948 by an American philologist, John S. Kenyon, when he discriminated between “cultural levels,” which refer to the degree of education and cultivation of a person, and “functional varieties,” which refer to the styles of speech suitable to particular situations. Thus, a cultivated person rightly uses informal or colloquial language when at ease with friends.

8. Dictionaries of the past have copied shamelessly from one to another, but the collecting of a file of illustrative quotations makes possible a fresh, original treatment. Scholarly works such as the OED and its supplements follow the canon of always using the earliest quotation and the latest for an obsolete word; in between, the quotations are selected for revealing facets of usage or for “forcing” a meaning. The criterion of use by only the best writers does not hold for a truly historical dictionary, because a “low” source may be especially revealing. The giving of exact source citations is not a matter of pedantry but establishes the scientific basis by which others can check the evidence. A different set of quotations, accurately attested, might have led to a different treatment. Thus, the phrase illustrative quotation is something of a misnomer, for the quotations are more than illustrative; they form the basic evidence from which conclusions are drawn. It is the work of the editor to decide when the collections are sufficient—ripe, as it were—to move from the collecting stage to the editing stage.

9. The development of machine aids, such as the computer, during the 20th century was heralded by some as ushering in a new era in lexicography. Although a computer can do well in many tasks of great drudgery that are involved in building a dictionary—mechanical excerpting of texts, alphabetizing, and classifying by designated descriptors—it is limited to what a human being tells it to do. It is difficult for a computer to sort out homographs (i.e., separate words that are spelled alike); at the editing stage, the delicate decisions must be humanly made. A computer can be used to good advantage in the compilation of concordances of individual authors or of limited texts, and then one type of dictionary could be made by a summation of concordances. Such a procedure, with a large body of literature such as that of the Renaissance, is especially advantageous because an editor would be overwhelmed working alone without any technological assistance.

10. Without a doubt, dictionaries have been a conservative force for many hundreds of years, not only in countries that have had an official academy that has the national language as part of its province but also in the English-speaking countries, in which academies have been spurned. Well-entrenched popular attitudes account for this. A Neoplatonic outlook assumes that there exists an ideal form of language from which faltering human beings have departed and that dictionaries might bring people

closer to the perfect language. Also, there is a widespread “yearning for certainty,” a seeking for guidance amid the wilderness of possible forms. Thus, people welcome self-proclaimed “supreme authorities.”

Used literature:

1. Chambers 20th Century Dictionary, Great Britain, 1983.
2. Macmillan English Dictionary, Great Britain, 2007.
3. Большой Англо-русский словарь, Moscow, 1972.
4. The Merriam Webster Dictionary, the USA, 2018.
5. Oxford Dictionary of Current English, Great Britain, 2006.

